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1

Heptacos-3-en-25-one—A New Unsaturated Ketone from *Ajuga bracteosa*†

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AJUGA bracteosa (Labiateae) is a perennial herb occurring in Western Himalayas from Kashmir to Nepal^{1,2}. The leaves are diuretic, stimulant¹ and used as a substitute for Cinchona³. The plant is also reported to possess cardiostimulant action in animals⁴ and anticancer activity in rats and mice⁵. Previous work on this plant includes isolation of saturated and unsaturated acids⁶, insect antifeedant diterpenes^{7,8} and insecticidal diterpenes⁹. In continuation of our work on the aerial parts of this plant¹⁰, we now report a new unsaturated ketone.

The air-dried powdered aerial parts of *A. bracteosa* were extracted with *n*-hexane and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure which in turn was subjected to vacuum liquid chromatography (VLC)¹¹ using silica gel as adsorbant. Compound **1** was eluted in hexane and was found to be homogeneous on tlc, **1** m.p. 70–71°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1610, 820 (unsaturation), 1710 (keto function), 1380 (CH₃) and 715, 710 cm⁻¹ (straight chain); *m/z* 392 corresponding to C₂₇H₅₂O. The base peak at *m/z* 57 and other abundant ion at *m/z* 335 formed by the α -fission of the CO group located it at C-25 whereas the other characteristic ions at *m/z* 363, 337 and 55 established the position of the double bond at C-3. These fragmentations are depicted on the structure. These data suggested the structure of **1** as heptacos-3-en-25-one which is in full accord with its ¹H nmr spectrum (80 MHz; CDCl₃) displaying resonances at δ 0.90 (6H, t, *J* 8Hz, two terminal CH₃), 2.35 (4H, t, *J* 8Hz, two CH₂ adjacent to CO function), 5.32 (2H, t, *J* 6Hz, olefinic function), 1.60 (4H, m, two CH₂ adjacent to double bond) and 1.25 (36H, brs, eighteen CH₂ of chain).

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Rapid Tlc Separation of Aromatic Amines on Surfactant Impregnated Silica Gel-G Plates

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AROMATIC amines are of considerable importance in industrial, toxicological and pharmaceutical applications¹. Keeping this in view tlc separation and detection of various aromatic amines have been carried out by several workers on various adsorbents². Duncan *et al.*³ analysed aromatic amines by tlc on cellulose impregnated with bis-(2-ethylhexyl)hydrogen phosphate. Yasuda⁴ carried

TABLE 1— R_f (X 100) VALUES OF AROMATIC AMINES*

Sl. no.	Amines	Silica gel-G		Silica gel-G + 1% Triton-X 100	Silica gel-G + 1% tetrabutyl ammonium bromide	Silica gel-G + 1% sodium lauryl sulphate	Silica gel-G + 1% acetoacetanilide
		(1)	(2)	(1)	(1)	(1)	(1)
1.	Aniline	78	3	83	96	73	82
2.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	82	1	78	99	81	89
3.	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	88	16	86	88	76	46
4.	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	96	6	91	28	68	91
5.	<i>o</i> -Aminophenol	23	20	23	90	94	23
6.	<i>m</i> -Aminophenol	71	8	97	80	35	57
7.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenol	17	7	17	8	38	53
8.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	70	51	59	94	90	74
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	57	61	39	86	77	7
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	1	64	69	84	72	94
11.	<i>o</i> -Phenetidine	88	5	92	73	70	55
12.	<i>o</i> -Anisidine	79	13	91	82	71	62

*Average of two identical runs : 15 cm in 40 min ; Solvent system : (1) 90 ml benzene+10 ml ethyl acetate, (2) 1% Triton-X 100.

out tlc of aromatic amines on cadmium acetate impregnated silica gel-G.

The present paper reports the resolution of twelve aromatic amines on various surfactant impregnated silica gel using benzene-ethyl acetate (90 : 10, v/v) as the solvent system.

Experimental

The solvents employed were freshly dried and distilled. An ascending irrigation technique was employed using glass plates (20×20 cm). The twelve aromatic amines were carefully recrystallised before spotting. Following adsorbents were used : (i) silica gel-G (E. Merck), (ii) silica gel-G (E. Merck) with 1% Triton-X 100, (iii) silica gel-G (E. Merck) with 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide, silica gel-G (E. Merck) with 1% sodium lauryl sulphate, and (iv) silica gel-G (E. Merck) with 1% acetoacetanilide.

The plates (thickness 0.5 mm) prepared with a Stahl type applicator using a slurry of the above adsorbents in distilled water, were dried for 24 h at 60±1°. The solutions of aromatic amines in acetone were spotted on the plates. In case of acetoacetanilide as the adsorbent, the diazotised amines were spotted at low temperature. The plates were dried at room temperature and then irrigated with benzene-ethyl acetate (90 : 10, v/v) solvent system. The yellow or orange spots could be observed without any visualising agent. However, more dilute amine solutions (0.1 µg) could be visualised by

exposing them in iodine chamber. R_f values of the various aromatic amines are listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The amines when spotted and irrigated on chromatographic plates resolved quite distinctly. Thus, all the 12 amines could be resolved. The best separation of amines was observed using silica gel-G impregnated with 1% Triton-X 100 adsorbent. Whereas, proper separation was not achieved on silica gel impregnated with tetrabutylammonium bromide, sodium lauryl sulphate and acetoacetanilide. A 1% Triton-X 100 was also used as solvent system but good separations could not be achieved (Table 1).

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